

ANALYSIS OF SOURCES AND WORKS OF SOURCE VALUE IN THE STUDY OF THE HISTORY OF AMIR TEMUR'S RELATIONS WITH INDIA

Odinayeva Umida Usmonovna

independent researcher of Bukhara State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14498565>

Annotation: This article is an analysis of works of source and source value in the study of the history of Amir Temur's relations with India. In particular, the systematic analysis of data on the comparative and analytical analysis of sources created during the reign of Sohirqiran Amir Temur.

Keywords: Sohirqiron, Source, Historiography, Historiography, Historiography, Calligraphy, Publishing, Secretarial, Translator, Linguistic, "Zafarnoma".

Historical sources and works of source value created during the reign of Amir Temur and the Timurids have been of interest to historians of all times. Uzbekistan's role in international relations was considered necessary in the coverage of the diplomacy of the past centuries of modern history, the victory marches of Sohirqiran to conquer world trade markets. Some issues of this topic are also reflected in the studies of the Amir Temur and Timurid periods. The works written so far can be divided into several groups according to their periodical, territorial, ethnic and religious principles.

First, the works created during the Amir Temur and Timurid periods;
Second, scientific, artistic and material works written during the years of the Russian Empire and Soviet power;

Thirdly, works, studies and dissertations covering the history of Amir Temur and Timurids during the years of independence;

Fourthly, Foreign Literatures;

Fifth, works created on the basis of scientific, historical approaches reflecting the history of the Indian land;

Correspondence and letters from Sixths, Ambassadors, Merchants, Travelers are an important resource.

The Qur'an was written in Persian by Nizamiddin Shami (1401-1402). [3] The work was completed in the spring of 1404 and presented to Amir Temur, who was returning to Samarkand after a seven-year march in Azerbaijan. The events that followed until the death of the Prophet were later recorded by Hafizi Abri. In 1400-1404, Amir Temur's munshi and secretaries wrote in Persian and Turkic, as well as his own experiences during the marches of 1400-1404, and

Giyosiddin Ali's work *Ruznamei gazavoti India* (Diary of a March). "Zafarnoma" is a historical work of the 14th-15th centuries during the reign of Amir Temur and the Timurids, Central Asia, the Six. This disambiguation page lists articles associated with the title Amir Temur. This is followed by a detailed account of Amir Temur's marches in the second half of the 14th century and the beginning of the 15th century. Due to the reliability of the historical information it collects, Zafarnoma became the main source for a number of works from the 15th to the 16th centuries. Only 2 manuscript copies of Zafarnoma have survived. The first is a copy of a manuscript presented to Amir Temur, copied in 1425, which is kept in the library of the Nuri Osmaniye Mosque in Istanbul (No. 3367). The second is a copy copied from 1434 from a manuscript distributed by the author to Amir Temur's grandson Mirzo Umar bahodir ibn Miron Shah, which is kept in the library of the British Museum in London (No. 23980). The textual scholar Felix Tauer uses copies of "Zafarnoma" from the history of Amir Temur - another important source - Hafizi Abru. Based on this edition, "Zafarnoma" was translated into Turkish in an abbreviated form (Ankara, 1940); Translated into Uzbek (Tashkent, 1996, compiled by O. Boriev) with preface, indicators and scientific commentaries. He consulted with experts and scholars in the field in solving every issue of national importance. In 2010, the Khmer Rouge was founded in 1955 and was founded in 1955. Alisher Navoi liked Amir Temur's interest in science and spiritual intelligence. Navoi said, "Wherever Temur met the people of science, culture and art, he would take them under his patronage, show them respect, give them importance to their upbringing, and use them as nadim (advisers) in his oliy majlis and in other positions." Tashkent city was founded in 1945. New markets and trading floors will be built. Klavikho spoke about the abundance and cheapness of wheat and rice in the Samarkand markets, and presented the city's handicrafts - satin, kimkhob, various yarn and woolen woven goods, fur and silk coats, attor's goods, spices and spices

During this period, Amir Temur and his exiled nobles Sultan Mahmudkhan controlled the Great Silk Road, the main international trade route from China and India through Central Asia to the Middle East and Europe, took important measures to ensure the safety of trade caravans, the construction of rabots, fortresses, and bridges, and paid great attention to the comprehensive development of trade and embassy ties between East and West. Most importantly, Amir Temur made a great contribution to the economic and cultural development of not only Movarounnahr, but also the countries of the Far and Middle East, as well as the rapprochement of peoples and countries.

Amir Temur established direct trade and diplomatic relations with major European kingdoms, such as France, England, and Castile. In 1915, Abdurazzak Samarkandi wrote a poem and a treatise on Arabic grammar, but the only surviving historical work is *Matla'i sadayn ve majma'i bahrain* (The Rising of the Two Crucifixible Stars and the Place of Two Seas Joining). The work is written in Persian and consists of two sentences. Abdurazzak Samarkandi wrote the work mainly between 1467 and 1469, and continued it again in 1470, finishing it in the same month. The first volume of *Matla'i Sa'dayn* briefly introduces the Iranian ruler Abu Sa'id (1316-1335), a descendant of Genghis Khan, and then begins the history of Amir Temur, and in general from 1304 to 1405 is given information on the history of Central Asia, Afghanistan, Iran, Azerbaijan, partly India and other countries. The history of Amir Temur died in Uthor in the year 17, 807 (February 18, 1405) and his grandson Khalil Sultan ascended the throne in Samarkand. In the preface of the second volume, the author begins the events from the time of Shohruh's accession to the throne in Herat (March 1405), saying that he wants to talk about the descendants of Amir Temur. Then, after mentioning the Timurids who ruled after Shahrukh (d. 1447): Mirza Abulkasim Babur, Sultan Abu Sa'id and other princes, Husayn concludes the work with information about the second time that Hussein Boyqara killed Yodgor Mirza in Herat and ascended the throne for the second time. This disambiguation page lists articles associated with the title Sánchez. A chronicle of the earlier parts of the work from the period of the author's life (mid-15th century) is compiled on the basis of the earlier work. Summing up the events of 1427, Abdurazzak Samarkandi himself said: "Hafizi Abru wrote . . . This is where *Zubdatu-t-tavorihi Boysunguri* ended," he says, noting that his main source is this work. It is noteworthy that Abdurazzak Samarkandi's *Matla'i sadayn* (*Matla'i sadayn*) was famous in its time and was recognized by a number of historians. Later, the work was recognized in Europe as a rare and reliable source on the history of socio-political, economic, cultural and international relations of the Timurid era, and parts of it were published several times from the 19th century onwards in French, English and Russian. The Persian text was published in 1936 in Lahur (Pakistan) by Muhammad Shafeh, a textual historian and researcher. The Events of 1405-1427 (Volume I, Part 1) was published in Uzbek in 1960 with a Persian text in 1442-1444. In 1992, Giyosiddin Naqqosh's diary of his trip to China, which was included in this part of *Matla'i Sadayn*, was published in Uzbek. Parts 2-3 of Volume II of the work have also been translated into Uzbek, but have not yet been published.

List of references:

1. Амир Темур жахон тарихида / Масъул мухаррир: Х-Кароматов. Муаллифлар жамоаси: С.Саиддосимов (рахбар), А.Ахмедов, Б.Ахмедов ва бошқ. Тулдирнлганва кайта ишланган иккинчи нашри. — Т.: Шарк, 2001. – Б. 561.
2. Madraimov, Abdumajid. Manbashunoslik: Bakalavriatning tarix yo'nalishi talabalari uchun darslik. A. Madraimov, G. Fuzailova. Т.: O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashriyoti, 2008.
3. U.Odinayeva. Temuriylar va Hindiston mumtoz adabiy asarlarining miniaturalar bilan bezatilishi va jahon madaniyatiga ta'siri//. Sharq qo'lyozma san'ati: an'anaviylik va zamonaviy yondashuv [Matn] : to'plam / muharrir G. Qarshiyeva; tuzuvchi A. Raxmatullaeva, Z. Asqarova, S. Azizxonova, L. Isamuhamedova, Z. Nosirova, D.Hojiboeva. – Toshkent: San`at jurnali, 2024.- B.181-184.
4. Kenjayev S.N. Amir Temur's Ambassadorial Activity in Diplomatic Relations with China (Min State) (In the Case of Fu An) // ISSN-L: 2544-980X.- Miasto Przyszłości Kielce, 2022.112-114 P. (Impact Factor: 9.2)
5. Kenjayev S. The importance of the northern and southern network of the great silk road in Amir Temur's relations with China. «Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: nazariya va amaliyot» nomli ilmiy, masofaviy onlayn konferensiya, (2022), № 28.-P 207–209.

